

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14480028

Towards Enhancing Crowd Control in Recreation Parks: Case for Effects of Inadequate Planning on the User's Comfort

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ABSTRACT

Inadequate planning of recreational parks in Nigeria has led to significant challenges in urban areas. Crowd control and user safety are seriously threatened by Nigeria's recreational facilities' poor design and administration. It has been noted that during busy times, recreational parks are consistently packed, which makes visitors unhappy and negatively impacts their well-being by creating stress and pain. This is acknowledged as one of the primary elements influencing how visitors view green spaces. The purpose of the study is to look into how users' well-being is affected by poor crowd control planning in recreational parks. By properly designing leisure areas to handle big crowds during extreme events, the goal is to increase safety and security. The methodology is a descriptive survey approach based on a thorough assessment of the literature, physical measurement of the components being assessed in the recreation parks, and observation of particular aspects. To gather pertinent data for the study, a self-made structured questionnaire was dispersed at random among the recreation park users. The study's conclusions draw attention to the shortcomings in the planning of recreational parks, the creation of design techniques such as signage and sufficient paths for crowd control, and the suggestions made to enhance the design for safety and security during events and emergencies in such public areas. To prevent crowd congestion, the study concludes that standards for planning and developing recreational parks with a focus on crowd control must be developed. It also suggests that proper consideration be given to the appropriate proportion of inhabitants in an area of space.

Keywords: Crowd control, Comfort, Inadequate planning, Recreation parks, Wellbeing

INTRODUCTION

To maintain public safety and improve urban life, recreational parks must be properly planned for crowd control. Setting appropriate criteria for recreational facilities is crucial, taking into account variables like land availability and population thresholds (Wash *et al.*, 2022). Planning for urban parks is difficult because of non-use, which highlights how crucial recreational planning is to community growth (Kyari *et al.*, 2023). Given recent world events, real-time crowd density analysis and management are becoming more and more crucial for public safety (Daware and Dhote, 2023). Preparation for the event, communication, monitoring, control techniques using signs, and emergency readiness are all examples of best practices for crowd management (Daware and Dhote, 2023). The establishment of dynamic urban built environments and the protection and enjoyment of tourists depend on the careful planning and administration of recreational areas (Emechebe, 2020).

Abbott and Geddie (2000) posited that efficient crowd control reduces liability and guarantees safety at events and sites. But research has revealed that certain recreational centers put profit ahead of patron safety, employing inefficient crowd control techniques that endanger guests (Okanigwe *et al.*, 2024; Etu *et al.*, 2024). Using thorough crowd management strategies, such as appropriate site planning, real-time monitoring and analysis, clear communication, and emergency readiness, is crucial to improving public safety (Daware & Dhote, 2023). Recreation parks may make crowd management procedures much better and lower the risk of mishaps or disasters by taking care of these issues, which will ultimately make the park a safer place for guests.

Digital signage for crowd management and evacuation instructions in parks has been studied. According to studies, digital signage can be utilised to adaptively control the flow of people during evacuations and obtain more attention than standard emergency exit signs (Adachi & Takahashi, 2019; Takahashi & Ichinose, 2017). Real-time sensing of traffic information is more effective for pedestrian flow, but human assistance is favoured for comfort, according to experimental studies that examined various information provision techniques and guidance methodologies (Feliciani *et al.*, 2020). The efficacy of digital signage-based emergency guidance systems has been assessed using simulations (Takahashi & Ichinose, 2017).

Furthermore, in contrast to conventional public signage, augmented signage has been suggested as a scalable way to offer customised navigation assistance in congested areas, perhaps increasing usability, decreasing task load, and boosting navigation performance (Hamhoum and Kray, 2011). According to these results, augmented and digital signage may be useful instruments for managing crowds in parks for recreation. Research on recreational parks and crowd control highlights several challenges and strategies. In recreational establishments such as casinos, improper planning and execution of crowd management techniques may endanger users (Etu *et al.*, 2024). Underuse of urban parks is frequently caused by poor maintenance, services, and amenities, which are frequently brought on by a lack of professional resources, finance, and security (Kekere and Eja 2024).

Crowd satisfaction is influenced by a variety of factors, including age and user expectations; appropriate planning, facilities, and post-event reflection are important components (Filingeri *et al.*, 2017). Crowding in parks is a complex issue influenced by visitor type, encounters, and location. Managers must carefully assess when increased use turns into "crowding" and put the right measures in place, like creating quality standards, assessing crowding norms, and using carrying capacity frameworks (Manning 2007; Çetinkaya *et al.*, 2024). Enhancing crowd management and visitor satisfaction in recreational parks necessitates thorough planning, sufficient funding, and attention to the various requirements and expectations of users.

Crowding is a significant source of stress for people and is acknowledged as one of the primary variables influencing visitors' experiences in green spaces (Manning *et al.*, 2000). Similarly, metropolitan public parks in Nigeria suffer from neglect and inadequate upkeep, resulting in reduced benefits to the built environment and a lower quality of life for city people (Kyari *et al.*, 2023). Recreational facilities in Asokoro District, Abuja, confront challenges such as encroachment from other land uses, large distances, insufficiency, and poor upkeep (Bogoro, 2018). These issues underscore the need for better design, development, and management of recreational spaces in Nigeria.

Research on park tourism and recreational facilities highlights significant gaps in crowd control and management strategies. Inadequate planning for crowd control in recreational parks is evident, with Daware & Dhote (2023) emphasizing the importance of pre-event preparation, crowd

monitoring, and emergency response. Etu *et al.*, (2024) reveal that ineffective crowd control measures in casinos put users at potential risk, suggesting similar issues may exist in other recreational settings. Bogoro, (2018) notes that urban recreational parks are often underutilized due to poor services and facilities, with a lack of finance, professional human resources, and absence of policies contributing to inadequate management and planning.

These studies collectively indicate a critical need for improved crowd control strategies, better resource allocation, and comprehensive policies to enhance safety and user experience in recreational parks and similar venues. The following objectives guide the research (i) To determine the user's perception of excessive crowds in the recreation parks (ii) To determine the areas most visited by the users in the amusement parks (iii) To determine the possible effects of inadequate planning on the users of recreation parks

LITERATURE REVIEW

The history of planning and crowd control in recreational parks has evolved significantly over time. Early Park planning was largely concerned with aesthetics and design (Hourakhsh *et al.*, 2020), but eventually changed to accommodate social and environmental objectives (Ayeni, 2017). Crowding became a key issue in park administration, prompting the creation of theoretical frameworks and empirical studies to assess and regulate visitor experiences (Manning *et al.*, 2000). As cities expanded, parks faced issues in reconciling greater recreational facilities with ecological services (Arku *et al.*, 2016). Measuring crowding standards, applying carry capacity frameworks, and implementing educational programs to change visitor behaviour are examples of modern park management practices (Manning *et al.*, 2000).

The history of planning and population control in recreational parks has changed dramatically, driven by rising demand for outdoor leisure and the need to successfully manage crowding. Early advocates, such as Frederick Law Olmsted, stressed parks' social and health benefits, laying the framework for urban park design and development (Olmsted, 2020). The emphasis has evolved over time to understanding visitor interactions and crowd management using empirical research and theoretical frameworks.

Historical Context

- **Frederick Law Olmsted's Influence:** His designs for urban parks aimed to improve public health and provide accessible recreational spaces, addressing social issues of his time (Olmsted, 2020).
- **Emergence of Recreation Planning:** The need for structured planning arose as recreational activities began to compete for space, leading to conflicts and the necessity for compatibility assessments (Marcouiller *et al.*, 2008).

Crowd Management Strategies

- **Theoretical Frameworks:** Research has established normative theories that differentiate between use levels and crowding perceptions, guiding management practices (Manning *et al.*, 2000).
- **Empirical Applications:** Studies, such as those conducted in Acadia National Park, have measured visitor norms and identified factors influencing crowding, informing management strategies (Manning *et al.*, 2000).
- **Zoning and Education:** Effective crowd control involves zoning conflicting uses, setting carrying capacities, and implementing educational programs to modify visitor behaviour (Manning *et al.*, 2000) (Vizor and Stephen-Obagah 2024).

While the focus has been on managing crowding and enhancing visitor experiences, some argue that the increasing commercialization of parks may detract from their original purpose, potentially leading to further conflicts and crowding issues.

Negligence in the development and management of these facilities has resulted in reduced benefits to the built environment, including decreased beauty, health, leisure activities, and community engagement (Officha *et al.*, 2013; Kyari *et al.*, 2023). Urban dwellers are increasingly recognising the value of quality parks in their daily lives, prompting a rethinking of park design to match changing demands (Kyari *et al.*, 2023). Distance, high transportation costs, and inadequate facilities for population thresholds exacerbate these concerns (Wash *et al.*, 2020). To resolve these issues, comprehensive landscape design, aesthetic management, and development control are required

(Officha *et al.*, 2013; Ifebi *et al.*, 2024). Furthermore, maintaining equal distribution and proper location of recreational facilities is critical to creating a more friendly and sustainable urban environment (Wash *et al.*, 2020).

The design of walkways and site planning strategies significantly influence crowd distribution and flow in recreation parks. Effective planning can enhance visitor experience by optimizing movement patterns and minimizing congestion. The following sections outline key aspects of how these factors impact crowd dynamics.

Walkway Design and Capacity

- Walkway width and flow rates are critical; optimal service levels are defined at 2 to 10 pedestrians per minute per foot of walkway width (Pushkarev *et al.*, 1975).
- Wider walkways accommodate higher densities, reducing bottlenecks and improving overall flow.

Spatial Layout and Accessibility

- The arrangement of pathways affects visitor movement; parks with interconnected spaces and high syntactic accessibility promote increased activity levels (Mohamed *et al.*, 2023) (Chen *et al.*, 2024).
- Facilities should be strategically placed along accessible routes to encourage diverse usage and minimise noise disturbances from active areas (Mohamed *et al.*, 2023).

Visitor Flow Coordination

- Site planning must consider visitor preferences and potential congestion points; personalised routine can enhance the experience by reducing wait times at attractions (Xu *et al.*, 2015).
- Effective logistics, such as the placement of moving walkways, can further streamline crowd movement and improve safety (He *et al.*, 2024).

Conversely, while optimised pathways and strategic site planning can enhance crowd flow, poorly designed spaces may lead to overcrowding and diminished visitor satisfaction, highlighting the need for continuous assessment and adaptation in park design.

Urban parks in Nigeria confront issues due to inadequate planning and development, resulting in diminished benefits to the built environment (Kyari *et al.*, 2023). The quality of natural soundscapes in parks is controlled by vegetation density and weather conditions, which influence human acoustic perception and comfort (Nwankwo *et al.*, 2022). Anticipation, amenities, and planning all have an impact on crowd satisfaction at events, as do age and user expectations (Kendrick *et al.*, 2012). Despite the Master Plan's provision for green spaces and recreational amenities in Abuja, its development and implementation have been hampered. According to a survey, more than 35% of recreational facilities in Phase 1 have changed land use, while only 11% of sporting facilities were built following the Master Plan (Ezeamaka and Oluwole, 2016). These findings underscore the importance of better planning and administration of urban parks and recreational areas in Nigerian cities.

Crowd control in recreational areas is an important issue that necessitates appropriate management solutions. Research recommends a variety of techniques for improving public safety and visitor experience. Real-time crowd density analysis can be used to efficiently monitor and control crowds (Daware & Dhote, 2023). Implementing normative guidelines for optimal use levels, as well as frameworks such as the Limits of Acceptable Change can help alleviate crowding issues (Manning *et al.*, 2000). Wireless sensor networks can monitor crowd behaviour and avert unwanted situations during huge gatherings (Kasudiya *et al.*, 2019). However, the efficacy of crowd management measures is dependent on their appropriate implementation by designers and construction professionals (Etu *et al.*, 2024). Pre-event planning, crowd monitoring, clear communication, and emergency readiness are all essential management approaches (Daware & Dhote, 2023). Adopting these evidence-based practices can help recreation parks enhance crowd management and visitor safety.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive research approach was used to collect data for this study to meet the study objectives. This research method involves direct observation and detailed investigation of the sample population. A cross-sectional field survey was carried out to assess user perceptions. Outdoor parks, both domestic and foreign, were observed. The evaluation was carried out by closely inspecting outdoor

park areas and their crowd control measures. The cross-sectional survey approach makes use of statistical data provided by survey respondents who complete questionnaires. Users were randomly distributed 120 questionnaires, 100 of which were returned for the study in various Abuja locations. Careful examination of the overall planning and arrangement, as well as the methods for controlling and managing crowd flow in the selected amusement parks. The crowd management measures that were implemented were also documented to ascertain their impact on users. In addition, users were asked to determine their degree of satisfaction with current crowd management techniques. Secondary data was gathered through a review of relevant literature on spatial design and crowd control as a technique for improving tourist experiences, reducing congestion, and mitigating safety issues. These include properly cited and referenced content from books, journals, periodicals, seminar papers, and internet sources.

3.1 Study Area

The research was carried out in Nigeria's capital city, Abuja, also known as the Federal Capital Territory. The city is now made up of six area councils: Abaji, Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC), Bwari, Gwagwalada, Kuje, and Kwali. The city is located at 9.07°N and 7.6°E and covers 1769 square kilometres (Figures 1 and 2). It is bordered by Kaduna, Kogi, Nasarawa, and Niger states to the north, south, east, and west, respectively. Abuja, Nigeria's Federal Capital Territory (FCT), is known for its vast green spaces and leisure facilities. Its natural spaces, controlled by the Department of Parks and Recreation, provide a beautiful balance of nature and urban living, highlighting the city as a model for sustainable development. The city accommodates various recreational parks, which many users frequently visit.

Figure 1: Map of Nigeria Showing FCT

Figure 2: Map of Abuja Showing AMAC

Data Presentation

Quantitative data presentation involves arranging the analysed data that has been collected and

interpreting the obtained findings or results. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22 was utilized to analyse the quantitative data. To display the results, tables, and charts were utilized while photographs were represented as plates for better comprehension of the results

4.0 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents data concerning Section C of a study, specifically focusing on the number of cases analyzed, the reliability coefficient, and its interpretation. In this instance, Section C encompasses a total of two cases. The reliability of the data collected from these cases is quantified by a coefficient of 0.708. This value falls within the range that suggests moderate to good reliability, indicating that the measurements or assessments conducted in this section are reasonably consistent and dependable. In the context of scientific research, reliability is a crucial aspect as it reflects the extent to which the results can be replicated under similar conditions. A reliability coefficient above 0.7 is generally considered acceptable, suggesting that the findings from Section C can be trusted to some degree. However, it is important to note that the limited number of cases only two may impact the robustness of the reliability assessment. Therefore, while the coefficient indicates a satisfactory level of reliability, further investigation with a larger sample size would be beneficial to enhance the validity and generalizability of the results.

Table 1: Reliability test

Section	Cases	Reliability	Interpretation
Section C	2	0.708	

The data presented in Table 2 provides a demographic overview of the respondents in the study, focusing on age, gender, and occupational category. Starting with age distribution, a significant majority of the respondents, accounting for 62.7%, fall within the 18-25 age bracket. This suggests that the study predominantly captures the perspectives of younger individuals, which may influence the overall findings. The next largest group is those aged 26-36, comprising 17.6% of the respondents. This indicates a smaller yet notable representation of young professionals or early-career individuals. The age groups of 37-47 and 48 and above are less represented, with only 11.8% and 7.8%, respectively. This skew towards younger respondents may reflect the target demographic of the research or the accessibility of the survey to younger populations.

In terms of gender distribution, the respondents are relatively balanced, with 52% identifying as male and 48% as female. This near-equal representation allows for a more comprehensive analysis of gender-related perspectives within the study, minimizing potential biases that could arise from a disproportionate gender ratio. Regarding occupational categories, the majority of respondents, 48%, are students, indicating that the study may be particularly relevant to the academic community or younger individuals still in education. Workers represent 23.5% of the sample, while graduates account for 17.6%. The self-employed category is the smallest, comprising only 10.8% of respondents. This distribution highlights the predominance of students and workers in the sample, which may influence the context and applicability of the research findings to these groups.

Table 2: Demographics of respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Age	-	
18-25	64	62.7
26-36	18	17.6
37-47	12	11.8
48 and above	8	7.8
Gender		
Male	53	52
Female	49	48
Category		
Student	49	48
Graduate	18	17.6
Worker	24	23.5
Self-employed	11	10.8

The data presented in Table 3 provides insights into visitors' experiences and perceptions regarding an amusement park, focusing on their frequency of visits, comfort levels concerning crowd sizes, exploration of attractions, feelings of discomfort due to overcrowding, and evaluations of safety and security measures within the park.

In terms of visitation frequency, the majority of respondents (50%) reported that they visit the amusement park rarely, while 29.4% indicated that they visit sometimes. A smaller proportion of visitors, specifically 9.8%, visit often, and only 2% visit the park always. Notably, 8.8% of respondents have never visited the park. The mean value of 2.46 suggests that, on average, visitors tend to fall into the "rarely" category regarding their frequency of visits. When assessing comfort levels related to crowd sizes during weekend visits, the data reveals that 43.1% of respondents sometimes feel comfortable with the crowd levels. Additionally, 32.4% reported feeling rarely comfortable, while 11.8% often feel comfortable. Conversely, 10.8% of respondents indicated that they never feel comfortable due to crowd levels. The mean value of 2.618 indicates that, overall, visitors tend to experience a moderate level of comfort regarding crowd sizes during their visits.

Regarding the exploration of attractions within the park, a significant majority (78.4%) of respondents acknowledged that there are specific attractions or areas they have not yet explored, while 21.6% stated that they have explored all areas of the park. This finding suggests a potential opportunity for the park to encourage visitors to discover lesser-known attractions. The survey also inquired about discomfort experienced due to overcrowding in specific areas of the park. A substantial 75.5% of respondents reported experiencing discomfort in certain attractions due to high crowd levels, whereas 24.5% disagreed. This indicates that overcrowding is a notable concern for many visitors, potentially impacting their overall enjoyment of the park.

Finally, when evaluating the overall safety and security measures within the amusement park, the responses were relatively balanced. While 43.1% rated the safety measures as good, 42.2% considered them fair. Only 2.9% rated the safety and security as excellent, and 11.8% deemed it poor. The mean value of 2.373 suggests that visitors generally perceive the safety and security measures as fair, indicating room for improvement in this area. In summary, the findings highlight key areas of visitor experience at the amusement park, including visitation frequency, comfort levels regarding crowd sizes, exploration of attractions, experiences of discomfort due to overcrowding, and perceptions of safety and security. These insights can inform park management strategies aimed at enhancing visitor satisfaction and overall experience.

Table 3: To determine the user's perception of excessive crowds in the recreation parks

Variable`	Frequency (percentage)	Mean value
How frequently do you visit this amusement park Never Rarely Sometimes Often Always	9 (8.8) 51(50) 30(29.4) 10(9.8) 2(2.0)	2.46
How comfortable do you feel in terms of the crowd level when you visit the amusement park on weekends Never Rarely Sometimes Often Always	11 (10.8) 33(32.4) 44(43.1) 12(11.8) 2(2.0)	2.618
Are there any specific attraction or places you have not explored here in this park? Yes No	80(78.4) 22(21.6)	1.216
Are there specific attraction or areas in this park where you experience discomfort due to overcrowding Yes No	77(75.5) 25(24.5)	1.245
How would you rate the overall safety and security measures within this theme park Poor Fair Good Excellent	12(11.8) 43(42.2) 44(43.1) 3(2.9)	2.373

The insights into the visitation patterns of respondents at a specific park, highlighting both the areas users frequent and those they tend to avoid. In terms of attractions visited, the highest percentage of respondents, 27.33%, indicated that they typically visit the rides and attractions, suggesting that these features are a significant draw for visitors. Following this, 22.09% of respondents reported visiting the restaurant, indicating a strong interest in dining options available within the park. The zoo attracted 14.54% of visitors, while the gardens were frequented by 13.37%. The arcade, although popular, was the least visited area, with only 17.44% of respondents indicating they explore this attraction during their trips. (See Table 4)

Conversely, when respondents were asked to specify areas or attractions they do not explore, the event center emerged as the least visited, with 26.77% of respondents indicating they do not engage with this area. The arcade was also noted by 16.54% of respondents as a non-visited attraction, followed closely by the restaurant at 15.75%. Both the rides and attractions and the zoo had equal responses, with 14.96% of respondents stating they do not visit these areas. The gardens, while moderately popular, also saw a notable percentage of 11.02% of respondents indicating they do not explore this attraction. This dual perspective on visitation patterns provides valuable information for park management, highlighting both popular attractions and areas that may require further engagement or development to enhance visitor experience.

Table 4: To determine the areas most visited by the users in the amusement parks

Variables	Frequency (percentage)
What areas or attractions within this park do you typically visit during your trips?	
Arcade	30(17.44)
Restaurant	38(22.09)
Rides and Attractions	47(27.33)
Zoo	25(14.54)
Event centre	9(5.23)
Gardens	23(13.37)
Specify which area or attractions you don not explore here in this park. Arcade	
Arcade	21(16.54)
Restaurant	20(15.75)
Rides and Attractions	19(14.96)
Zoo	19(14.96)
Event centre	34(26.77)
Gardens	14(11.02)

Table 5 shows the effects of inadequate planning on users of the recreational park. From the analysis, 52.9% of the respondent felt good about all the facilities and attractions when exploring the park, 43.1% felt fair with a mean value of 2.5 which implies that the respondent felt good about all the facilities and attractions when exploring the park. 70.6% of the respondents agreed that the park had enough spaces and facilities strategically place to benefit them during their visit while 29.4% disagreed. 68.8% of the respondent agreed that they easily find their way through the park and back when exploring the park while 31.4% disagreed. 37.3% of the respondents are likely to return to the park based on their experience in its organization and arrangement of its features while 43.1% were neutral about it, 7.8% agreed that it is very likely for them to return to the park while 4.9% agreed that is very unlikely and 6.9% agreed that it is unlikely for them to return to the park with a mean value of 3.36 which implies that the respondents were neutral about the subject.

Table 5 To determine the possible effects of inadequate planning on the users

Variable	Frequency (percentage)	Mean value
How do you feel about all the facilities and attractions when exploring this park		2.5
Poor	4(3.9)	
Fair	44(43.1)	
Good	54(52.9)	
Excellent	0	
Do you think this park has enough spaces and facilities strategically placed to benefit you during your visit		1.294
Yes	72(70.6)	
No	30(29.4)	
When exploring this park, do you easily find your way through the park and back		1.314
Yes	70(68.6)	
No	32(31.4)	
How likely are you to return to this park based on your experience in its organization and arrangement of its features		3.363
Very unlikely	5(4.9)	
Unlikely	7(6.9)	
Neutral	44(43.1)	
Likely	38(37.3)	
Very Likely	8(7.8)	

Signage and walkways play a crucial role in crowd control and safety in recreational parks. Wayfinding signage increases visitors' confidence, perception of safety, and motivation to walk further while reducing anxiety. Adachi & Takahashi, (2019) stated that digital signage can effectively control evacuation flow and manage congestion in crowded areas. Path design and physical features significantly influence visitor behaviour, with signage and parking area placement being important predictors of spatial patterns. Effective crowd management strategies include pre-event planning, real-time monitoring, communication, and emergency preparedness. These elements are essential for ensuring public safety and enhancing the overall experience in recreational spaces. By implementing well-designed signage systems and walkways, park managers can better control crowd flow, improve visitor navigation, and create a safer environment for all users. Plate 1, 2, 3 and 4 shows the signage and walkways used to control crowds in the study location.

Plate 1: Signage used to control crowds in the recreation park in Abuja

Plate 2 Signage used to control crowds in the recreation park in Abuja

Plate 3: Walkways used to control crowd in the recreation park in Abuja

Plate 4: Walkways and adequate site planning used to control crowd

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study looks into the effects of inadequate site planning on controlling overcrowding in the construction of an amusement park in Abuja, Nigeria. According to the study, the site layout of the

recreational parks in the study area is poor, resulting in increased crowding and stress for users of the facilities. This study emphasises the importance of using spatial characteristics and planning to reduce overcrowding in amusement space design. Controlling crowd movement in an amusement park is essential for maintaining everyone's well-being and safety while minimising discomfort and uneasiness. By focusing on spatial layout, it is clear that strategic design may make a significant impact in keeping the fun running smoothly throughout the park, especially at peak periods. It is not enough to simply place boundaries or signs; it is also necessary to create a layout that feels natural, guiding people where they need to go without their knowledge. This study found that a deliberate, organised design area may transform turmoil into a smooth flow of enthusiasm. Flexibility and technological integration are critical for future designs, as layouts must be able to adapt to changing visitor patterns and needs while also controlling crowds to maintain safety and security. The study proposes that a flexible and sustainable design be used in leisure parks so that the spaces available can handle varying crowd sizes and activities. There is a need to include technology into these park spaces to assist in monitoring and identifying potential overcrowding areas, as well as planning an easy flow of movement behind the scenes to balance things out. Smart technology could be the key to effective crowd management in a recreational environment. Also, instead of bombarding people with signs at every turn and region, place them wisely and provide official directions and instructions. Use visible landmarks or natural flow to direct people without them realising it.

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